

A HYBRID DAMAGE DETECTION SYSTEM FOR COMPOSITE PRESSURE VESSEL

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ABSTRACT

Composite pressure vessels (CPV) have been considered to be the most promising candidate for high pressure storage of liquid and gaseous fluids. Because of this, there is an increasing demand for CPVs in the automotive industry and the space industry. However, the safety of CPVs is always a critical issue. And due to the limited knowledge in failure mechanisms in composite, CPVs are usually designed with a high safety factor. That leads to comparably high weights. One possibility to reduce that conservatism and therefore to save weight is to gain knowledge of structural mechanical behavior in real time. With a Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) system, the changes in the structural performance of CPVs can be determined and further can be translated into damages or degradations to ensure safety and extend service life. This paper proposes a hybrid damage detection method which contains the strain monitoring method and the mode shape curvature node (MSCN) method. The MSCN-based method is validated with an analytical model and a numerical model. An analytical study is conducted on a free-free beam to construct the relationship between MSCN and damage location as well as damage severity. Then, the proposed MSCN-based method and the strain monitoring method are adopted in monitoring the CPVs. The results demonstrate that the hybrid method can be applied for damage detection with a relatively small number of sensors.

1 INTRODUCTION

Over the last decades, there is an increasing demand for pressure vessels in automotive industry and space industry. Due to the benefits in weight reduction, cost reduction and safety, Composite Overwrapped Pressure Vessels (COPVs) have been considered to be the most promising candidate for high pressure storage of liquid and gaseous fluids [1]. Since the failure mechanism in composite is not clear yet, COPVs are usually designed with a high safety factor which leads to comparably high weights.

COPVs are made of a liner and a surrounding overwrap [2]. The liner is mainly made of the aluminum or the high-density polyethylene (HDPE) which is functioning as a barrier and isolation for the fluid. The surrounding overwrap is normally made of carbon fiber composite which can provide the strength to prevent the liner from burst or leakage. Within the overwrap the resin sustains shear-loads and keeps the fibers in position, while the fiber provides the tensile strength. Due to heterogenic and anisotropic nature of the composite, the material behavior is more complex compared to all-metal vessels. Furthermore the interaction between the liner and the overwrap leads to a complex structure. Thus a wide range of different defects can occur during operation.

Over-pressurization will lead to a disbond between the liner and the composite overwrap. Crack initiation and crack propagation in matrix and liner can be caused by various influences, e.g. environmental ingress. Impact can cause cracks in the matrix or the liner, fiber breakage and delamination. As a result, the impact induces a stress concentration [3] and a local loss of stiffness. Very intense impacts can also cause indentations or even through-holes between composite and liner. Impact damages on outer layers of composites can also result in a loss of burst strength. Damage

caused by impacts can occur beneath the surface without noticeable defects on the outer surface, which exclude visual inspection as a reliable NDE method [4].

In order to adequately detect and locate damage on pressure vessels in the early stage, a suitable testing method must be applied to prevent the vessel from unexpected burst and hazardous consequences resulted from human and environment.

According to the standard ISO 11623 [5] "Gas cylinders - Composite construction - Periodic inspection and testing", gas cylinders are required to be recertified with hydrostatic testing every two to five years. But some researchers point out that hydrostatic testing is not adequately sensitive to detect local impact damage [3]. In addition, the test procedure required 150 % of the level of maximum operating pressure, which may introduce damage or make existing flaws to grow. At last, the test sequence is time consuming. Thus, the overall cost is increased due to the out-of-service time.

Non-destructive testing (NDT) can be utilized as a recertification method for maintenance issues, such as visual inspection, ultrasonic C-scan, acoustic emission (AE), shearography, eddy current, X-ray and thermography [6]. However, visual inspection cannot detect the damage inside the structure, such as delamination. Ultrasonic Phased Array can scan the structure with a swept ultrasonic beam, by sending a wave into the structure and investigate the reflected waves, the flaws can be detected. AE adopts the idea that under mechanical loading, the damages will generate elastic waves. The waves will propagate in the structure and can be acquired by the sensors. Laser Shearography can detect the discontinuity on the surface under load case. Although these NDT methods provide numerous possibilities to investigate component, these methods are still time consuming and need expensive equipment. In addition, since the composite vessel consists of different layers and materials, some NDT applications might have problems in accessibility and accuracy.

Therefore there is a significant meaning to introduce the idea of the condition-based maintenance in COPV. With an online Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) system, the changes in performance of COPV can be determined and further can be translated into damages and degradations to reduce weight, save costs and ensure safety.

In this paper, typical SHM methods for COPVs are reviewed at first. Then the mode shape curvature node (MSCN) -based method is studied by analytical methods. The relationship between the modal strain at nodes and the crack location as well as severities is investigated on a free-free beam with analytical method. Then, the proposed MSCN-based method and the strain monitoring method are adopted in monitoring the CPV. The results demonstrate that the hybrid method can be applied for damage detection with a relatively small number of sensors.

2 REVIEW OF CURRENT SHM METHODS FOR COPVS

Structural health monitoring (SHM) has become one of the most important topics for aircraft structural engineers, as for its benefits in enhancing safety, lightweight and reducing life-cycle cost [6]. There are many emerging new SHM technologies: Guided wave, acoustic emission, vibration, strain, and sensor rupture. In addition, sensor technologies are mostly studied in PZT, fiber optic, MEMS, nanotube, etc. Among them, vibration based SHM technology has been demonstrated to be one of the most reliable method [7].

A lot of researchers proposed SHM systems based on the strain monitoring function of fiber optic sensors. They try to monitoring the strain distribution over the whole vessel.

Kunzler [8] investigated the influence of pressure cycles and impacts by measuring the axial and transverse strain fields with multi-axis fiber grating sensors. They proposed a process to locate and quantify cut fibers and delamination defects. Their results are compared with conventional NDT method, e.g. ultrasonic and eddy current methods. According to [9] the NASA Nondestructive Working Group developed three generations of sensor-integrated COPVs. The first attempt to create a 'smart' COPV was achieved by using the surface-mounted fiber Bragg grating (FBG) multi-axial grids. Klute [3] embedded a circumferentially-wrapped optical fiber sensor with a helical pitch along the axis of the composite vessel. The sensor is interrogated by optical frequency domain reflectometry (OFDR), which allows strain measurements at various locations along the fiber. Each fiber sensor indicates a unique random pattern of reflections which forms the baseline for monitoring. Strain results in a shift of this pattern compared to the baseline. Finally, a Fourier transform calculates strain and location out

of the provided pattern. The presented configuration not only provides precise strain distributions, but also detects and quantifies the occurred defects.

Acoustic emission is also studied by lots of researchers. Kalafat and Sause [10] used acoustic emission source to localize the damage in a type III CFRP pressure vessel.

Methods based on Guided Wave (GW) are promising methods for COPV. Since GW is sensitive to small damages and can travel a long distance along the structure. McKeon [11] investigated the propagation of Ultrasonic Guided Waves (UGW) in thick-walled COPV structures. Therefore a piezoelectric transducer is attached to the outer surface of the vessel to generate UGWs. The excited propagating waves are received by a laser vibrometer measuring the out-of-plane velocity. Thereby the experimental setup allows detecting impact damages and is recommended for further applications. Another implementation of a SHM approach on CPVs was achieved by [12]. During manufacturing, a PZT sensor network is successfully applied with in total eight embedded sensor strips (five PZT disks per strip). While the circumferential spacing of all strips is set to 45°, four of the strips were attached above the aluminum liner and four remaining strips were embedded beneath the hoop layer of the outer surface. In this application the sensor network is especially suited for detecting and localizing impact damage.

Vibration based SHM technology has been demonstrated to be one of the most reliable method. Zhou [13] used modal properties and dynamic response to detect the damage on a composite fuel tank.

Most of the methods require lots of sensors to be applied on the structure. This paper proposes a hybrid damage detection method which contains the strain monitoring method and the mode shape curvature node (MSCN) -based method. The MSCN-based method proposed in this paper is based on the mode shape curvature (MSC) which has demonstrated to be effective in damage detection [14]. Different from the MSC-based method, the MSCN-based method need a relatively small number of sensors for damage detection and it does not relay on the reference data. In addition, the strain monitoring method and the MSCN-based method in the hybrid method share the same set of sensors. The strain monitoring method can detect the damage closed to the strain gauge by monitoring the changes in strain, while the MSCN-based method can detect the damage along the whole structure.

Figure 1: Typical SHM systems (a) Fiber optical sensors [3], (b) Acoustic emission [10], (c) Guided Waves with piezoelectric sensor array [12] and (d) Modal properties [13]

3 ANALYTICAL STUDIES ON MSCN

In this section, a free-free Euler-Bernoulli beam with an open crack is considered as the physical model. Parametric studies are conducted to investigate the influence of the location and severity of the damage on the displacement of nodes.

3.1 From mode shape to mode shape curvature

Under the assumption that a mode shape exists, the deflection of an Euler-Bernoulli beam follows

$$\begin{aligned} w^{(4)}(\xi) - \lambda^4 w(\xi) &= 0 \\ \xi &= \frac{x}{L}, \quad x \in (0, L), \quad \lambda^4 = \frac{\rho \omega^2}{EI} L^4 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where w represents the lateral deflection of the beam, x is the coordinate in the longitudinal direction, L is the beam length, ρ is the density, ω is the natural frequency, E represents the Young's modulus and I is the moment of inertia of the cross section.

The solution for Eq. (1) is found to be

$$w(\xi) = c_1 \cos(\lambda \xi) + c_2 \sin(\lambda \xi) + c_3 \cosh(\lambda \xi) + c_4 \sinh(\lambda \xi) \quad (2)$$

where c_1 , c_2 , c_3 and c_4 are the coefficients which can be determined by entering the boundary conditions.

For a free-free beam, the boundary conditions are as follows.

$$w''(\xi) = 0, \quad w'''(\xi) = 0, \quad \text{both at } \xi = 0 \text{ and } \xi = 1 \quad (3)$$

By substituting the boundary conditions defined in Eq. (3) into Eq. (2), a homogeneous linear system of equations is given by

$$\mathbf{A} \{c_1 \ c_2 \ c_3 \ c_4\}^T = 0 \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 \\ -\cos(\lambda) & -\sin(\lambda) & \cosh(\lambda) & \sinh(\lambda) \\ \sin(\lambda) & -\cos(\lambda) & \sinh(\lambda) & \cosh(\lambda) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

The condition for a homogeneous linear system with nonzero solution is $|\mathbf{A}|=0$, which delivers the natural frequency equation

$$\cos(\lambda) \cosh(\lambda) = 1 \quad (6)$$

After satisfying the natural frequency equation shown in Eq. (6), the value of λ can be acquired. The coefficients in Eq. (2) are the solution set of the homogeneous linear system, so the mode shape can be written as

$$w(\xi) = \cos(\lambda \xi) + \cosh(\lambda \xi) + C(\sin(\lambda \xi) + \sinh(\lambda \xi)) \quad (7)$$

where

$$C = \frac{\cos(\lambda) - \cosh(\lambda)}{\sinh(\lambda) - \sin(\lambda)} \quad (8)$$

As we assume a linear strain distribution along the thickness direction, the MSC which is the second derivative of the mode shape can be transform into the modal strain by multiplying the coefficient h . Thus, the modal strain at the surface can be expressed as

$$\varepsilon(\xi) = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial \xi^2} h = \lambda^2 h (\cos(\lambda \xi) - \cosh(\lambda \xi) + C(\sin(\lambda \xi) - \sinh(\lambda \xi))) \quad (9)$$

where h is the distance from the neutral axis to the surface.

The mode shape curvature node (MSCN) is the stationary point where the value of the modal strain is zero at the corresponding mode. Figure 2 illustrates the first three mode shape and mode shape curvature of a free-free beam. Mode 2 has one MSCN in the middle ($\xi_2 = 0.5$) as shown in Figure 2 (e), while mode 3 has two MSCNs ($\xi_1 \approx 0.36$, $\xi_3 \approx 0.64$) as shown in Figure 2 (f). Therefore, mode 2 and 3 are taken into consideration. The strain values at the MSCNs in the intact state equal to zero.

Since the parameter λ in Eq. (7) and Eq. (8) is governed by Eq. (6) which is independent to the material properties, the MSC in Eq. (9) does not rely on the material properties of the structure. For example, when the stiffness EI is changed, value of λ will not change, because the natural frequency ω will have another value according to Eq. (1). This means that the position of the MSCN does not depend on the material properties of the structure. This can be recognized through the fact that the position of the MSCN is not affected by environmental parameters such as temperature or humidity. This is the key characteristic to develop a baseline-free damage detection method in this paper.

Figure 2: Mode shape (a) 1st mode, (b) 2nd mode, (c) 3rd mode and mode shape curvature (d) 1st mode, (e) 2nd mode, (f) 3rd mode

3.2 MSCN changed by crack

According to Chondros [15], a beam with a crack can be modelled as two beams connected by a rotational spring. If the crack is located at $\xi_s = s/L$, the mode shapes of the two beams can be expressed as

$$w(\xi) = \begin{cases} c_1 \cos(\lambda \xi) + c_2 \sin(\lambda \xi) + c_3 \cosh(\lambda \xi) + c_4 \sinh(\lambda \xi) & \xi \in (0, \xi_s) \\ c_5 \cos(\lambda \xi) + c_6 \sin(\lambda \xi) + c_7 \cosh(\lambda \xi) + c_8 \sinh(\lambda \xi) & \xi \in (\xi_s, 1) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Thus, the modal strain is as follows.

$$\varepsilon(\xi) = \begin{cases} -\lambda^2 h (-c_1 \cos(\lambda \xi) - c_2 \sin(\lambda \xi) + c_3 \cosh(\lambda \xi) + c_4 \sinh(\lambda \xi)) & \xi \in (0, \xi_s) \\ -\lambda^2 h (-c_5 \cos(\lambda \xi) - c_6 \sin(\lambda \xi) + c_7 \cosh(\lambda \xi) + c_8 \sinh(\lambda \xi)) & \xi \in (\xi_s, 1) \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

The boundary conditions at both ends are the same as in Eq. (3). The continuity conditions due to the crack are displacements, moments, and shear forces at both ends of the crack. In addition, the discontinuity in rotation angle at the crack location is caused by the moment. The boundary conditions can be written as

$$w(\xi_s^+) = w(\xi_s^-), \quad w''(\xi_s^+) = w''(\xi_s^-), \quad w'''(\xi_s^+) = w'''(\xi_s^-), \quad \mu w''(\xi_s) = w'(\xi_s^+) - w'(\xi_s^-) \quad (12)$$

where $\mu = EI / KL$ is the dimensionless cracked section flexibility which represent the severity of crack and K represents the stiffness of the spring.

Similarly, after substituting the eight boundary conditions given in Eq. (3) and Eq. (12) into Eq. (10), an 8×8 homogeneous linear system is defined as

$$\mathbf{B} \{c_1 \ c_2 \ c_3 \ c_4 \ c_5 \ c_6 \ c_7 \ c_8\}^T = 0 \quad (13)$$

where

$$\mathbf{B} = \begin{bmatrix} -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & 0 & 1 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -fc & -fs & fch & fsh & fc & fs & -fch & -fsh \\ fs & -fc & fsh & fch & -fs & fc & -fsh & -fch \\ fc & fs & fch & fsh & -fc & -fs & -fch & -fsh \\ -fs - \mu\lambda fc & fc - \mu\lambda fs & fsh + \mu\lambda fch & fch + \mu\lambda fsh & fs & -fc & -fsh & -fch \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -\cos(\lambda) & -\sin(\lambda) & \cosh(\lambda) & \sinh(\lambda) \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \sin(\lambda) & -\cos(\lambda) & \sinh(\lambda) & \cosh(\lambda) \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

in which

$$fc = \cos(\lambda\xi_s), \quad fs = \sin(\lambda\xi_s), \quad fch = \cosh(\lambda\xi_s), \quad fsh = \sinh(\lambda\xi_s) \quad (15)$$

The condition for linear system Eq. (13) to have a non-zero solution is

$$|\mathbf{B}| = 0 \quad (16)$$

Eq. (16) is also called the natural frequency equation. The solution of Eq. (16) leads to the value of λ in different modes. In addition, after satisfying the natural frequency equation, the coefficients in mode shape Eq. (10) and Eq. (11) are the solution set of the homogeneous linear system \mathbf{B} .

The 2nd and 3rd modes are studied. For a certain crack location and a crack severity, the coefficients in Eq. (11) can be calculated from Eq. (16). Furthermore, the strain value at the MSCN of the chosen mode can be acquired. The effect of the crack location and the crack severity on the strain at the MSCN is parametrically studied. The location of the crack is studied from 0 to 1 with an interval of 0.01, while the severity is investigated from 0.01 to 10 with an interval of 0.001. As shown in Figure 3 - (c), (d) and (e), the abscissa represents the location of the crack and the ordinate represents the severity of the crack. The color represents the value of the strains at N_1 , N_2 and N_3 . Figure 3 - (c) is the strain at N_2 , while Figure 3 - (d) and (e) are the strains at N_1 and N_3 respectively.

Figure 3: Normalized modal strain (a) 2nd (b) 3rd and the value at the MSCN affected by crack location and severity (c) N_2 (d) N_1 (e) N_3

As the strain at the MSCN of the intact mode shape is always zero, the modal strain difference at the MSCN can be acquired just by the strain at the MSCN of the damaged beam. Thus, the strain difference can be used to constitute a baseline-free indicator. Furthermore, the strain at the MSCN is no longer zero when the crack appears. In addition, the strain at the MSCN will have a different response when the location or severity of crack changes. It can be concluded that when the crack is located at the place where the amplitude of the modal strain is large, the strain at the MSCN is noteworthy. The strain is limited when the crack located at the place near to the nodes.

When the threshold of the strain value at the MSCN is considered as 0.1, for the case of crack severity $\mu = 1$, the sensitive area of N_2 is $(0.17, 0.42) \cup (0.58, 0.83)$ in abscissa as shown in Figure 3 - (a). In addition, the sensitive area of N_1 and N_3 are $(0.12, 0.30) \cup (0.43, 0.59) \cup (0.69, 0.87)$ and $(0.13, 0.31) \cup (0.41, 0.57) \cup (0.7, 0.88)$ which are illustrated in Figure 3 - (b). Thus, most part of the structure (length from 0.12 to 0.88) can be recognized as a sensitive area.

4 A HYBRID DAMAGE DETECTION METHOD

In this section, a COPV is modeled with Abaqus. The MSCN-based method and the static strain monitoring method are investigated.

4.1 MSCN monitoring for COPV

The outer diameter of the vessel is 150 mm and the total length is 800 mm. Table 1 listed typical geometry parameters of the COPV. The liner is made of aluminum and the overwrap is made of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy composite layers. The material properties are illustrated in Table 2.

Two typical modes are taken into consideration as shown in Figure 4 (a) and (c). The natural frequency of the 1st mode is around 82.2 Hz, and it is 117.5 Hz for the 2nd mode. The figures illustrate the modal strain distribution which is vertical to the hoop direction on the structure. Instead of investigating the strain on the whole structure, only the strains at the node line are studied as illustrated in Figure 4. Since the strain at the node line is always zero, the MSCN-based method does not need a reference signal for damage detection.

Material	Layer	Layer angle (°)	Layer thickness (mm)
Aluminum	Liner	-	2.5
	1	90	1
	2	45	1
Composites	3	-45	1
	4	90	1
	5	-45	1
	6	45	1
	7	90	1

Table 1: Geometry parameters of the COPV.

Engineering constants	Aluminum	Composite layers	Damage area
Density (kg/m ³)	2700	1550	1550
E_1 (GPa)	70	142	14.2
$E_2=E_3$ (GPa)	70	8.5	8.5
$G_{12}=G_{13}$ (GPa)	26.3	3.7	0.37
G_{23} (GPa)	26.3	2.6	2.6
$\nu_{12}=\nu_{13}$	0.33	0.25	0.25
ν_{23}	0.33	0.42	0.42

Table 2: Engineering constants.

Figure 4: Modal strain distribution and damage location (a) 1st mode - Health, (b) 1st mode - Damage at D3, (c) 2nd mode - Health and (d) 2nd mode - Damage at D3

Figure 5: Sketch of the angle

In total five damages are deployed at different locations on the structure subsequently. The damage is simulated with a loss in stiffness. The material properties of the damaged area are listed in Table 2. The dimension of the damage is around 50mm×60mm (vertical to hoop direction× hoop direction). From the hoop direction, the damages are located at the place where θ equals to 300° as show in Figure 5. Figure 4 demonstrate the modal strain distribution of 1st and 2nd mode under health stage (a) and (c) and damage case (b) and (d) (the damage is located in D3 area). It can be seen that the damage introduced a strain concentration on the structure.

According to the analytical results in section 3, the damage will influence the strain value at the node. The strains which are vertical to the hoop direction at the node line are illustrated in Figure 6 (1st mode) and Figure 7 (2nd mode). It can be seen that on the node line, when θ is around 300° , the strain is significant.

In this model, a proper threshold can be 2×10^{-4} . As such, the sensitive area in the first and second mode of interested can be acquired as show in Figure 6 and Figure 7. The sensitive area of first mode is significant only in the case that damage locates at D5 area, thus the first mode is not efficient for damage detection. For the second mode of interested, the sensitive areas cover a wide region along the hoop direction. For the damage case D1, D2, D3 and D5 corresponding to Figure 7 (b), (c) and (d), the sensitive angle in the hoop direction is more than a range of 30° in a total 360° . In order to cover the whole structure, 12 sensors are sufficient. However, the MSCN is not sensitive to the damage located at D4 which is near the node line. Thus, the MSCN method can detect the damages on the structure, while it is not sensitive at the area with in the distance range between 50mm to 100mm to the node line which is the D4 area.

Figure 6: Strain distribution at the node line in 1st mode under different damage cases (a) health, (b) D1, (c) D2, (d) D3, (e) D4 and (f) D5

Figure 7: Strain distribution at the node line in 2nd mode under different damage cases (a) health, (b) D1, (c) D2, (d) D3, (e) D4 and (f) D5

4.2 Static strain monitoring for COPV

The static strain is an important indicator for the damage. The problem within the strain based method is that it is only sensitive to the damages near the sensor. In this application, the strain sensor can be used to locate the damage closed to the node line when the vessel is under pressure.

The inner pressure is set to be 20MPa, thus the average strain vertical to the hoop direction on surface of the overwrap is around $1800\mu\epsilon$ as show in Figure 8 (a). The same damage as the last section is taken into consideration. Figure 8 (b) illustrates the strain distribution that the damage is located at D3 area. A possible threshold for damages in this case can be $1800\pm 1000\mu\epsilon$ which is $800\mu\epsilon$ for the lower limit and $2800\mu\epsilon$ for the upper limit. Under the circumstance that a damage with a size of $50\text{mm}\times 60\text{mm}$ appears, the sensitive area where the strain value is exceed the threshold is around $125\text{mm}\times 150\text{mm}$ (vertical to hoop direction \times hoop direction). In the hoop direction, the sensitive angle area is around 56° . This indicates that only one strain sensor is needed for detecting damage in the area of $125\text{mm}\times 150\text{mm}$. Furthermore, when the strain sensor is located in the node lines, only seven sensors is needed to monitor the strain over the whole circle.

Figure 8: Strain distribution under static load (a) health and (b) Damage at D3

The insensitive area of the MSCN method is in the range of 50mm~100mm to the node line. This can be covered with the static strain monitoring method. By combining the MSCN method and the static strain monitoring method, the whole structure can be monitored with only 12 sensors since both methods can use the same set of sensors. In addition, the hybrid method can locate the angle of damage by identifying which sensor has an abnormal signal.

5 CONCLUSIONS

This paper reviews the advantages and disadvantages of current SHM methods which are used for COPVs. An analytical model is adopted to study the proposed MSCN-based method on a free-free beam. Furthermore, the areas which are sensitive to the damage are identified with the analytical model. After modelling the COPV with FEM, the MSCN-based method and the strain monitoring method are adopted for damage detection. The results demonstrate that the insensitive area of MSCN-based method can be covered by the static strain method. Thus, the hybrid method can detect the damage along the whole structure with only 12 sensors.

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